

CULTIVATE

Food Sharing Landscapes in CULTIVATE Hub Locations: Milan City Profile

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MILAN CITY PROFILE

Geography and Economy

Milan, with almost 1.4 million inhabitants, is the second most populous city in Italy after Rome and lies in the northern part of the country, at the centre of the Po Valley, surrounded by the Alpine Amphitheatre. The city is the capital of Lombardy (Regione Lombardia), the most economically prosperous area of Italy. Milan's Metropolitan Area (Città Metropolitana) comprises 3.25 million inhabitants and is the country's leading financial and industrial centre¹. The city is internationally well-connected and serves as a transportation hub for the country. The climatic conditions combined with the fertile alluvial soil of the Po Valley and the presence of many karst springs, have resulted in a rich agricultural territory². An important aspect of Milan's geography is its water management system for agriculture and the movement of goods, with a complex network of canals (Navigli). The Northern peri-urban areas and municipalities have historically housed Milan's industrial sites, shaping an urban continuum along the main transportation infrastructures. In contrast, the South maintained its rural economy and landscape.

In 2022, the Metropolitan Area produced 10% of the Italian GDP and hosts the national headquarters of 45% of the international companies in the country³. The main economic sectors are pharmaceuticals, biotechnologies, fashion, design, research and universities, communication, finance and IT services. Around 16% of the municipal area is devoted to agriculture, which makes Milan the second-largest agricultural Municipality in Italy for surface area and the first for productivity⁴. The Milan Metropolitan Area has a stronger economic and job market situation than the national average in Italy. However, the distribution of employment rates according to age groups reveals one of the challenges for the city: the employment rate in the 15-34 age group is 53%⁵. Despite its dynamic economy, Milan has struggled with two significant challenges in recent years: the stagnation of salaries and the rapid increase in rents, house prices and general inflation.

Milan's Metropolitan Area leads the innovation and IT sectors in Italy. According to the Experis Tech Cities report, the city is the first in Italy by job positions and production⁶. Milan hosts 12% of the Italian technology sector and 31% of the national ICT workforce. Thanks to several universities specialising in technology and medicine, Milan is a hub for innovation. In addition, the partnerships between companies, public administrations and industry associations have driven the development of several start-up incubators and accelerators. In 2022, 2,790 innovative start-ups were founded in the Metropolitan Area, accounting for 19% of the new companies founded in Italy that year⁷. Milan's Metropolitan Area has 100% broadband and 77% coverage by FTTH internet connections (ultra-broadband) in 2022, ranking the area as one of the most connected in the country⁸.

Politics and Society

Regarding sub-national governance, Italy is divided into nineteen regions and two autonomous provinces whose responsibilities are: education, social and healthcare systems, transportation and mobility, and territorial planning⁹. At the municipal level, Milan has a mayor and a city council elected every five years. Further, the city is divided into nine municipalities (Municipi), each with a president and a local council. They manage several public services (such as parks, welfare, mobility, culture, and education), along with the relationships between citizens and the public administration¹⁰. Moreover, the city is the primary centre of Città Metropolitana di Milano, which gathers 133 municipalities and is governed by the mayor

of Milan and the Metropolitan Council with responsibilities for territorial planning, education, public services, mobility, transportation and digitisation¹¹.

The socio-demographic conditions of the city and its metropolitan area are unusual compared to other Italian cities. Milan has one of the highest levels of graduates in the country¹², however, this is still lower than the EU27 average¹³. Foreign citizens comprised around 21% of the population in 2022, more than double the national average of nearly 9%. Almost half of these non-Italian citizens came from Egypt (15%), the Philippines (15%), and the People's Republic of China (12%)¹⁴. Milan has been a destination for internal Italian migration since the beginning of the 20th century and for international migrants since the 1980s, creating a multicultural and diverse society with a general openness towards migrants¹⁵. Indeed, this openness is visible in local policies and institutions, and in the concentration of private, third-sector and public initiatives devoted to hospitality, food sharing, healthcare and social services¹⁶.

Food and Food Culture

Historically, Milan had a strongly interconnected relationship with its surrounding rural areas, making it a hub for agricultural products and innovations. However, food poverty and security are a primary challenge for the city and its most vulnerable citizens. In particular, foreign families and the elderly living alone show the highest risk of economic poverty, resulting in lower access to food in terms of quality and quantity¹⁷. In response, Milan has an urban food policy with five priorities to create a more sustainable food system: (1) to ensure healthy food and water for all citizens; (2) to promote the sustainability of the food system; (3) to promote food education; (4) to reduce food waste; and (5) to support scientific research in agrifood sectors. The policy encourages private companies as well as public and third sectors to work on the five priorities to create an accessible and sustainable food supply chain through action at the municipal and metropolitan levels¹⁸. Furthermore, EXPO 2015, hosted by Milan, led international debates on urban food systems sustainability that culminated in the Milan Urban Food Policy Pact, signed by more than 260 cities worldwide¹⁹. The crucial role of the agrifood sector is also evidenced by planning policies and plans which aim to create agricultural parks in a belt around the city²⁰. In addition, there are Five Distretti Agricoli (Agricultural Districts) focused on enhancing the rural landscape of the Milan Metropolitan Area through collaborative governance between local citizens, the third sector and farmers²¹. Agrifood is recognised as a driver for improving the environment and progressing sustainable urban development²².

Milan has historically been the centre of a significant food production and commerce system. In addition to cattle breeding, dairy products, wheat and rice production, which are integral to Milan's traditional dishes, the city is a hub in northern Italy for redistributing national and international fresh goods. The wholesale fish, meat, and fruit and vegetable markets are the primary providers of national intermediary wholesalers²³. Moreover, migration has made Milan a place where different cuisines meet. It hosts international fairs, such as Fiera dell'Artigianato, TuttoFood, and the Milan Food Week, and organises events for traditional festivities with ethnic foods, such as the End of Ramadan and the Chinese New Year.

Environment and Sustainability

Improving the quality of the environment is one of Municipality and the Metropolitan Area's key objectives. Milan and the Po Valley have the poorest air quality levels in Western Europe, with an average PM2.5 concentration of 19.7 $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$ ²⁴. The city ranks 349th out of 375 cities in the European Environmental Agency's list of the cleanest urban areas²⁵. The Municipality developed Piano Aria e Clima – Plan of Air and Climate – to enhance the air quality and combat climate change and the urban heat

island effect in Milan²⁶. The Municipality of Milan is a member of the C40 Cities Climate Leadership Group, a global network of major cities aiming to take united action against climate change²⁷. Milan's municipal plans and policies also follow the 2030 UN Agenda, which aims to create a more sustainable city in relation to social, cultural, economic, and environmental dimensions. For example, the urban development plan (Piano di Governo del Territorio) encompasses the 15-minute city concept, which aims to build a more sustainable city by increasing residents proximity to social, educational, and healthcare services²⁸. Milan ranks at the top of Italy's most sustainable cities in terms of its social, economic and environmental indicators²⁹. Globally, however, the city ranks 51st in the Arcadis Sustainable Cities Index, and 21st for environmental sustainability³⁰.

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MILAN FOOD SHARING LANDSCAPE

Quantity

Number of FSIs: **107** (14 outside Milan and 93 in Milan) in **122 locations**

Population per FSI (1.363.411 inhabitants.): **12.624 inhabitants/FSI**

No. of translocal initiatives and online initiatives

6 FSIs are working within as well as beyond Milan. They are national or international initiatives and mainly share food and knowledge through redistribution and cooking/eating. Banco Alimentare, Progetto Arca, Equo Evento and Food For Life operate in other Italian cities and are focused on food redistribution. Food Wave and Food For Souls are international organisations devoted to sharing knowledge and networking.

In total, there are 4 FSIs without a physical location. Food Wave and Food for Souls are international networks that work online only and aims at building connections amongst entities devoted to create sustainable food behaviours and food systems. Libere Rape Metropolitane is an informal network and a blog that focuses on urban gardens, and Equo Evento is an association active in several Italian cities and is devoted to collecting food surplus in catering events.

No. of initiatives with multiple locations within the city and what they share.

8 FSIs operate over multiple locations and share mainly food and skills through redistribution and cooking/eating practices. IBVA, Emporio della Solidarietà, Pane Quotidiano and Opera San Francesco focus on the fight against food poverty and have worked in Milan for over 30 years, giving them a solid organisational structure with many volunteers, donors and stakeholders. In addition, Trattoria Solidale, Olinda, Mare Culturale Urbano, and Opera in Fiore are social enterprises focusing on job integration and reintegration for disadvantaged people – the first three initiatives are restaurants and the last one is devoted to agricultural activities.

Initiatives outside the Milan's administrative boundaries

The search found 14 FSIs operating outside the administrative border of Milan but inside the commuting area delimited by the OECD. The initiatives are mainly concentrated in the northern peri-urban municipalities, with 7 devoted to collective cooking/eating food, 2 to redistributing and 5 to growing.

Sector of sharing

FSIs were coded according to four sectors: growing, cooking and eating, redistributing and multifunctional, based on what their activities. The analysis consisted of summing the number of initiatives based on three categories of food sharing: growing, cooking & eating, and redistributing. Cooking and eating activities are grouped due to their similar function to provide meals for people. Nevertheless, we are aware that there are FSIs who are specifically involved in only one of the two activities (i.e., catering, delivery services, food processing, etc). FSIs were deemed as multi-functional if more than one function (growing, cooking & eating, or redistributing) was full-filled. The percentage of FSIs was calculated by dividing the number of FSIs assigned a specific type out of the total number of initiatives. Hence, the sum of all percentages is higher than 100%.

Table 1. Type of FSIs in Milan

Type of FSIs	No. of initiatives	% of initiatives
Cooking & Eating	43	40.2%
Growing	36	33.6%
Redistributing	51	47.7%
Multifunctional	36	33.6%

Figure 1. Percentages of the type of FSIs

Redistribution FSIs are predominant in Milan, with 47.7%. These FSIs are primarily devoted to collecting focus on collecting surplus food and distributing it through both national and European food assistance programs. In addition, 20 FSIs combine redistribution with Cooking and Eating and/or growing practices. Multifunctional redistribution FSIs are mainly organisations that have worked in Milan for decades, which gave them a solid organisational structure with many volunteers and a complex network with other associations, citizens and public administrations (i.e., IBVA, Banco Alimentare, Croce Rossa and Nessun Escluso). These initiatives collect and redistribute food to fight against poverty and have expanded their activities into innovative forms of redistribution (such as solidarity supermarkets). Cooking & Eating FSIs account for 40.2% of the initiatives. This may be related to the relevant presence of soup kitchens and other initiatives devoted to hospitality for people in need, such as Opera San Francesco, Pane Quotidiano and Cena dell'Amicizia. It is also related to the many restaurants and bars

Figure 3. The frequency of words in the FSIs online mission statements, goals and objectives

As shown in Figures 2 and 3 above, 'Social' is the first term in order of appearance and 'Garden' the second, accounts for the active gardening and horticulture activities in Milan, with frequent mention of terms such as 'vegetables', 'fruit' and 'producer'. As well, 'kitchen', 'meal' and 'soup' have a high frequency, indicating the significant number of FSIs devoted to sharing meals to people in need. Notable is the frequency of the terms 'association', 'community', 'need', 'family', 'social', 'inclusion' and 'reintegration', which reveals the primacy of social goals amongst FSIs in the city. In addition, 'job', 'reintegration', 'training' and 'restaurant' indicate the significance of labour integration through FSIs.

What is shared

Data on ‘what is shared’ was collected based on the activities of FSIs and further compiled in three broad categories: stuff, knowledge & skills, and spaces. We analysed the resultant data in two ways, first by the full range of elements being shared and then by broader categories of material stuff (Food; Meals; Plants; Seeds; Tools; Compost; Kitchen Devices), skills (knowledge and skills) and spaces (land and kitchen). To establish what is shared by FSIs in Utrecht the occurrence of each term in the three broad categories was counted and summed up. The percentage of FSIs sharing an element was calculated by dividing the sum of each term by the number of initiatives. For example, the code ‘food’ occurs 65 times, this would be divided by the total nr of FSIs identified in a city. FSIs can share more than one thing which means that the sum of percentages per category of things being shared will be greater than 100%.

Table 2. What is shared by category: stuff, space, & skills

Things	No. of initiatives	% of total initiatives	Terms	No. of initiatives	% of total initiatives
Knowledge & Skills	68	63.6%	Knowledge	67	62.6%
			Skills	25	23.4%
Stuff	84	78.5%	Food	65	60.7%
			Meal	33	30.8%
			Plants	19	17.8%
			Seeds	18	16.8%
			Compost	1	0.9%
			Kitchen Devices	4	3.7%
			Tool	3	2.8%
Spaces	8	7.5%	Kitchen Spaces	5	4.7%
			Land	3	2.8%

Table 3. Number of elements shared by FSIs

What is shared?	No. of initiatives	% of total initiatives
Share 1 thing	59	55.1%
Share 2 things	43	40.2%
Share 3 things	5	4.7%

Figure 4. Percentages of what is shared

Table 2 and Figure 4 reveals that FSIs focus primarily on sharing food and food-related stuff (food, meal, plants, seeds, compost, tools, kitchen devices) followed by 'knowledge & skills' and then 'spaces'. However, the analysis by single terms shows that 'knowledge' is the most recurring, accounting for 62.6% of FSIs. This term refers to direct or indirect educational and training activities aimed at promoting sustainable behaviours on food and its supply chain (from growing to waste reduction and management), the social and cultural values of food, and healthy diets. This reveals that FSIs know the importance of their dissemination role and expanding the capacity to embed sustainable habits amongst participants.

Worth noting is the limited presence of space sharing initiatives. Of the 107 FSIs, 8 rent or offer kitchen spaces or land lots, but none share spaces alone, rather they combine this with educational and redistribution activities. Only 3 initiatives share land lots to create urban gardens (Coltivando, Il Giardino degli Aromi and Orto in Città), and all have a primary educational objective rather than renting spaces for individual food production. The 9 Municipalities of Milan (the submunicipal administrations) already rent to citizens most of the individual urban gardens available in the belt parks around the city and certify that terrains are free from toxic agents. Indeed, many soils in Milan have high concentrations of them, which limits the possibility of creating 'legal' urban gardens for food production in the city.

Table 3 shows how many things (Knowledge & Skills, Stuff, Spaces) FSIs share. 55.1% are devoted to share only one thing, 40.2% two and 4.7% three. In addition, FSIs that share two things are mainly combine stuff and knowledge. The 5 initiatives sharing three things are Laboratorio di Cucina Pane Quotidiano, Piazza dei Mestieri, Servizio Formazione all'Autonomia which work for job integration for people in need, and Coltivando and Il Giardino degli Aromi two urban gardens.

Modes of sharing

FSIs in Milan adopt a range of different modes of sharing from bartering and gifting to selling and collecting. Bartering involves exchange of goods or services, gifting implies no monetary exchange, whilst selling can be not-for profit or for-profit. Collecting refers to activities such as gleaning or foraging. Data on approaches to sharing was taken from FSI profiles and allocated to one of these modes. Note, FSIs may use more than one mode of sharing across their activities. Data on FSIs mode of sharing was counted using the occurrence of representative codes, percentages were further calculated by dividing the occurrence of terms by the total number of initiatives. As certain initiatives use more than one mode of sharing, the resulting statistics do not add up to 100%.

Table 4. Modes of sharing

How is it shared?	No. of initiatives	% of total initiatives
Collecting	26	24.3%
Selling	40	37.4%
Gifting	73	68.2%
Bartering	20	18.7%
Multimodal	39	36.4%

Figure 5. Percentages of the modes of sharing

Table 4 shows that the primary mode of sharing food is gifting, 68.2% of the total FSIs mapped. Gifting includes providing meals, seeds, plants, and food surplus. The high presence of initiatives that use selling, 37.4%, may be related to the existence of many social enterprises which focus on job training and employment activation for vulnerable or marginalised people. Indeed, one-fourth of the total initiatives have this organisational form and are devoted to catering and food production. Multimodal sharing is active in 36.4% of FSIs. Collecting as a mode of sharing in Milan is, in all cases, combined with another mode, either gifting or bartering or both.

Organisational structure of initiative

FSIs in Milan adopt a range of organisational structures to operationalise their activities. While the definition and legal categorisation of organisational structures is not uniform across Europe such organisational analysis is still useful to delineate splits between for-profit and not-for-profit both within Milan and to compare activities between Milan and other locations. The organisational categories are based on but also extend those established in the SHARECITY project³¹. The identification and calculation of percentages of FSIs organizational mode followed the same procedure as for the other coding categories. The occurrence of an organizational term was counted and divided by the total number of FSIs. As FSIs can operate under more than one organizational framework the percentages do not add up to 100%. For example, an initiative can be registered as a non-profit, but can run a social enterprise to finance the non-profit activities.

Table 5 - Distribution of the organisational structure

Sharing Organizations	No. of initiatives	% of total initiatives
Charity	5	4.7%
Club	1	0.9%
Non-Profit	21	19.6%
Association	30	28.0%
Social Enterprise	26	24.3%
Network	8	7.5%
For-Profit	5	4.7%
Informal Network	5	4.7%
Cooperative	2	1.9%
Public Sector	4	3.7%

Figure 6. Percentages of the organisational structures

Data from Table 6 indicates a high presence of associations and non-profit initiatives, which appear to be related to the long standing focus on solidarity within Milan. Indeed, there are historical initiatives devoted to the fight against food poverty that date back to the sixties (i.e., Opera San Francesco and IBVA), and this aspect reveals a shared awareness of this focus in the city. Moreover, the historical relationships between Milan and food sharing appear in the relevant presence of social enterprises devoted to job integration and reintegration. Milan seems to be using FSIs as drivers to increase social inclusion and guarantee social dignity.

Technology

In order to be mapped the FSIs had to have a digital profile in the form of a website (or web application), Facebook, Twitter/X, or Instagram. Once identified FSIs were cross checked with the remaining social media platforms and via Google search engine to see if they had a presence or a website as FSIs often have a presence on more than one platform or have both a website and social media profiles.

Table 6. Distribution of used ICTs

ICT use	No. of initiatives	%of total initiatives
Website	101	94.4%
Facebook	81	75.7%
X/Twitter	20	18.7%
Instagram	52	48.6%

Figure 7. Percentages of the used ICTs

Almost all the FSIs have a website, which is used as an online manifesto and to give users basic information on the initiative, their mission, contacts, locations, and services. This indicates the increasing accessibility of websites. Social networks are also prevalent, and tend to be used to promote events and allow for direct contact and interaction with users. In this regard, Facebook and Instagram are the most used platforms, with only 20 initiatives having an x.com/Twitter profile and in many cases, their profiles were rarely updated. This is likely to be due to the changing nature and content of X/Twitter in recent years, which has become less productive as a community space. It is worth mentioning the presence of 6 FSIs that promote their activities exclusively through social networks: 4 are urban gardens, 1 a solidarity restaurant, and 1 an informal network.

SPATIAL ANALYSIS

The previous section provided an overview of the composition of FSIs within Milan. This section focuses on the location of FSIs. This spatial analysis is conducted only with FSIs with a physical location within Milan or its peri-urban area (as noted earlier, there are four initiatives without a physical location as they work online only). There are also eight cases where an FSI has multiple locations in the city; in these cases all the locations were mapped separately, resulting in 122 georeferenced points. There were also 14 FSIs operating outside the administrative boundary of Milan but within the commuting area delimited by the OECD, and these are included in the following maps. A range of spatial analyses follow, including: concentration of FSIs across Milan and the concentration by FSI sector.

Concentration Analysis

To work on homogeneous areas, the territory of Milan was divided in a hexagonal tile grid of 500m of radius. The analysis considers this grid as it refers to the '15-minute city' concept, which is used to define and improve welfare facilities in urban planning. Indeed, citizens have an average walking speed of 2 km/h on their daily movements to reach public services, green areas, public transport stops, supermarkets, and other essential services. This concept not only aims to increase the proximity to essential services but also the sustainability of the urban environment by reducing private and fuel-based mobility. Analysing FSIs and their concentrations from this perspective can offer interesting insight concerning their role in improving urban areas.

The number of FSIs existing in each tile were calculated and then categorised according to the sector of sharing (growing, cooking & eating, redistributing). Figure 9 below provides an overview of the concentration of FSIs across Milan, which is represented by a one-scale choropleth map.

Figure 8. Map of the concentration of all FSIs in Milan by Municipality

Although distributed across the city, Figure 9 above reveals a South West – North East concentration axis of FSIs in Milan. It starts from Municipality 6, passes through Municipality 1 and ends in Municipalities 2 and 3. These are the most densely populated areas in Milan.

Figures 10, 11 and 12 below present the location of FSIs by sector: growing, cooking & eating and redistributing.

Concentration Analysis: Growing

Figure 9. Concentration of FSIs which grow food in Milan by municipality

While there are multiple collective growing initiatives in almost every municipality, growing initiatives concentrate in peri-urban areas where the agricultural belt parks have driven the creation of urban community gardens in the last decades. Indeed, some of these initiatives are the legacy of the first urban gardens created between the 1960s and the 1970s when groups and individuals built their own vegetable gardens in peri-urban areas³². The growing initiatives closer to the centre are instead concentrated in residual spaces or private gardens. While primary and middle schools in Milan have their own educational vegetable gardens these are not mapped as FSIs in this case as they do not have an online presence.

Concentration Analysis: Redistribution

Figure 10. Concentration of FSIs which redistribute food in Milan by municipality

While each municipality has multiple initiatives that redistribute food there is a concentration of such activities in Municipality 1 (centre) and in Municipalities 2, 3 and 6 (south-west). The concentration in Municipality 2 may be related to Centrale Railway Station, which hosts several welfare services and facilities for homeless people. Across the city, redistributing FSIs follow the urban fabric, spreading out as they move away from the centre but close to areas with good accessibility to public transport (metro, bus, tramways and train stations).

Concentration Analysis: Cooking and Eating

Figure 11. Concentration of FSIs which cook and eat food in Milan by municipality

Cooking and Eating initiatives tend to be concentrated in the city centre and more densely populated areas. In particular, Municipalities 4 and 5 have lower concentrations, both with just two FSIs which provide cooking & eating activities. Their activities are often hyper-local in focus meeting specific local needs. Similarly to redistribution FSIs, there is a concentration of initiatives around Centrale Railway Station, which spaces host welfare services and organisations devoted to help migrants and homeless people.

FSIs Clusterisation

The categorisation of the sectors of sharing allows for developing a three-scales choropleth map, which shows the diversification level of the food sharing landscape in Milan. By blending colours (multiply), it reveals the presence of sectorial and multisectorial clusters of sharing across the city.

Figure 12. FSIs Clusterisation map

The map reveals a functional mix in the centre (Municipality 1) with most cooking/eating-redistribution (blue). In peri-urban areas, there is a concentration of growing and cooking/eating initiatives (orange) and growing and redistribution (green). In addition, several FSIs exclusively share food as eating/cooking (magenta), redistributing (cyan) and growing (yellow).

Demographic, Social and Economic Indicators

The concentration analysis set out above provides a clear picture of the locational aspects of FSIs, however geography alone cannot explain why FSIs locate in particular places. The following analysis explores whether there may be correlations between location of FSIs and other socio-economic variables, including the location of FSIs relative to: number of inhabitants per FSIs, population density, foreign populations, ageing index, education level, average individual gross income and employment. Due to data availability, the analysis is performed at the sublocal administration level of the 9 Municipi (Municipalities).

Inhabitants per FSI

Figure 13. Inhabitants per FSIs by municipality

As represented in Figure 14, the number of inhabitants per FSI is higher in Municipalities 1, 2, 3 and 6, which appears to be related to population density. The index is calculated over the 122 locations of the 107 FSIs mapped.

Population density

Previous research has demonstrated that dense populations provide the network effects needed to support ICT-mediated sharing. With this in mind, population density per municipality was layered over the location and the concentration grid of FSIs.

Figure 14. Population density and FSIs concentration by municipality

Figure 15. Inhabitants per FSIs (x) and population density (y)

Figure 15, the population density map of Milan, shows that the North-East axis is the most densely populated, while the South East and West areas show the lowest values. This echoes the historical division between the heavily industrialised northern peri-urban areas and the rural southern and western ones. The concentration of FSIs follows the same pattern, drawing a south-west/north-east concentration axis,

which starts from Municipality 6, passes through Municipality 1 and ends in Municipalities 2 and 3. Indeed, these are the most densely populated areas in Milan. The concentration of FSIs then follows the population density, albeit with a low correlation. The small number of data points mean no statistically significant correlation can be made. Figure 16 below illustrates the extent of correlation by plotting the number of inhabitants per FSIs (x) and the population density (y) of each municipality.

Foreign Population

Given the focus of many FSIs on supporting vulnerable or marginalised sections of society to integrate into communities, the concentration of foreign populations within municipalities was compared to the locational incidence of FSIs.

Figure 16. Percentage of foreign population and FSIs concentration by municipality

Figure 17. Inhabitants per FSIs (x) and % of foreign population (y)

The map (Figure 17) and graph (Figure 18) reveal no correlation between FSIs and foreign population. Municipalities 1, 2 and 6 have the highest concentrations of FSIs and different percentages of foreign population. In the same way, the other municipalities have similar foreigner presence and divergent FSIs concentrations (i.e. Municipalities 7 and 4). More comprehensive and nuanced data is required to explore correlations between vulnerable populations and FSIs. Below we explore whether there are any relations between age and FSI incidence, with the assumption that very young and very old populations may be considered vulnerable in certain contexts.

Ageing Index

Ageing index is a social indicator that reveals the age composition of a certain population. It is the percentage of residents above 65 years old over the population below 15. It was used in this context to explore the location of FSIs relative to this index which is shown below, Figure 19.

Figure 18. Ageing Index and FSIs concentration by municipality

The map cannot reveal any correlations between ageing indexes and FSIs concentrations as the age composition of Milan is similar amongst the municipalities. The difference, which is only 39% between the highest and lowest figures (Municipalities 2 and 6), does not provide a significant statistical indication across the municipalities.

Education level

The location of FSIs was considered in relation to educational attainment levels by municipality and shown in Figure 20 below. The education level is shown on the legend as the percentage of residents above 15 years old with higher education, understood as having a Bachelor's Degree at least.

Figure 19. Education level and FSIs concentration by municipality

Figure 20. Inhabitants per FSIs (x) and % of population with high education (y)

The map (Figure 20) and the graph (Figure 21) reveals no correlation between education levels and FSIs concentration. Municipalities 1 and 3 have high concentration of FSIs and high education levels. All the other Municipalities have similar education levels yet divergent FSIs concentrations. For example, Municipalities 2 and 7 have similar education levels and, respectively, the second-highest and lowest concentrations of FSIs – Municipality 2 has almost 2.5 times the FSIs of Municipality 7.

Individual Average Gross Income

As many FSIs focus on supporting sections of society considered vulnerable or marginalised, often due to low income, the individual annual average gross income was compared to the local incidence of FSIs, as shown in Figure 22. Due to data provided by the Italian Ministry of Finance and Economics, this map is broken down into Post Code Areas³³.

Figure 21. Average individual annual gross income and FSIs concentration by post code areas

Figure 22. Inhabitants per FSIs (x) and average individual annual gross income (y)

Figure 23 plots the average annula income and the number of inhabitants per FSI and reveals no correlations between incomes and the number of FSIs. Data shows divergent situations: the areas with the lowest and highest incomes have similar number of residents per FSI (4500 circa), while areas with average incomes around 30k €/year have different values.

Occupancy Rate

The map in figure 24 shows the % of the population between the ages of 15-65 years who are in work or training per municipality.

Figure 23. Occupation rate and FSIs concentration by municipality

Figure 24. Inhabitants per FSIs (x) and occupation rate (y)

Figure 25 shows that FSIs concentrate on areas with higher occupancy rates in Municipalities 2, 3 and 9. However, this seems to be related to population density as the graph in Figure 25 reveals no correlations between occupancy rate and the presence of FSIs.

Conclusion

This report documents the form, focus and location of FSIs across Milan and reveals a rich and diverse picture of the food sharing activities that operate within the municipality and its peri-urban area. Compared to similar mapping of Milan conducted in 2016³⁴ the number of FSIs has more than doubled which apparently indicates strong expansion of activities over the past decade. However, the previous mapping excluded FSIs devoted to the fight against food poverty, which may be the reason for the small number of entries. For example, initiatives such as IBVA, Caritas Ambrosiana and Opera San Francesco, which have been working in Milan for decades, were not included. In addition, most of the bottom-up FSIs mapped in 2016 are today inactive, such as Mercato Agrobiologico, Gnammo, Ratatouille App, Spesa della Memoria and Next Door Help. This comparison may reveal a weakness of FSIs developed by informal and bottom-up networks. They can rely on participants only who, at the beginning, lack a structured organisation and the support of local administrations or other entities. In addition, the debate and the reorganisation of the urban food system were at their embryonal phase in 2016 but rapidly evolved in the following years.

The urban food policy and its related activities could have improved networking amongst FSIs. This action has brought out initiatives that were working alone, including them into a more comprehensive network amongst public, private and third-sector entities. In addition, new regulatory frameworks, such as Legge Gadda which regulates food surplus management³⁵, have offered opportunities to develop new initiatives, especially in food surplus collection and redistribution. Before the implementation of these frameworks, initiatives worked in a sort of legal vacuum without solid administrative support.

The increase in social enterprises in the last decade may be a reason behind the expansion of FSIs in Milan. Many restaurants, bars and agricultural companies devoted to job integration and reintegration for fragile people have been created since then, and their role as drivers for social inclusion has increased in importance for local communities and media presence.

Finally, web development has become more accessible during the last decade in terms of technical skills and costs required. This aspect, alongside the increased use of social networks, has offered the initiative the opportunity to improve their online presence, share their activities and have better media relevance. While mapping is essential for locating practices within the city, it is also a necessary step for establishing any unevenness in distribution by different sectors of FSIs across the city. Various socio-economic variables were compared with the incidence of FSIs to explore whether any correlations emerged. No strong correlations were identified, although the limited availability of granular data and the low number of FSI data points restricts the level of statistical analysis that can be undertaken.

Further in-depth exploration of the drivers behind the establishment (or not) of particular FSIs in specific locations will be further explored through the CULTIVATE project running until December 2026.

¹ <http://dati.istat.it/>

² <https://www.britannica.com/place/Milan-Italy>

³ Centro Studi Assolombarda (2023). Milano ancora in espansione, pil su dell'1% nel 2023. In: Sole 24 Ore, February 24th 2023. https://www.ilsole24ore.com/art/milano-ancora-espansione-pil-dell-1percento-2023-AE0vGQoC?refresh_ce=1

⁴ Abis, M., Airolidi, A., Araniti, A., Goggi G., Jabes, D., & Nuzzo, G. (2016). Osservatorio sulla Città Metropolitana di Milano: Report 2016.

https://web.archive.org/web/20170926114435/http://www.group.intesasanpaolo.com/script/sir0/si09/contentData/view/OssCittaMetropolitana_2%20Report_Completo016.pdf?id=CNT-05-00000004C7944&ct=application%2Fpdf

⁵ <http://dati.istat.it/index.aspx?queryid=25524#>

⁶ Experis (2023). Tech Cities Report April 2023. https://info.manpower.it/hubfs/TechCities_aprile_2023.pdf

⁷ Camera di Commercio Milano, Monza Brianza, Lodi (2022). *Il Sistema ICT*.

<https://ester.milomb.camcom.it/sites/default/files/ricerca/allegati/Dossier-Il-Sistema-ICT.pdf>

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- ⁹ Costituzione della Repubblica Italiana. <https://www.gazzettaufficiale.it/eli/id/1947/12/27/047U0001/sg>
- ¹⁰ <https://www.comune.milano.it/comune/palazzo-marino/municipi>
- ¹¹ Statuto della Città Metropolitana di Milano
https://www.cittametropolitana.mi.it/export/sites/default/portale/conosci_la_citta_metropolitana/Statuto_regolamenti/doc_pdf/Statuto_Citta_metropolitana_Milano_16_12_2021.pdf
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- ¹³ https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/EDAT_LFSE_03_custom_7700237/default/table?lang=en
- ¹⁴ <http://sisi.comune.milano.it/>
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- ¹⁸ <https://www.milanurbanfoodpolicypact.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/10/Milan-Food-Policy-ENGLISH.pdf>
- ¹⁹ <https://foodpolicymilano.org/milan-urban-food-policy-pact/>
- ²⁰ https://www.cittametropolitana.mi.it/parco_agricolo_sud_milano/
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https://www.urbanit.it/wp-content/uploads/2020/10/BP_Branduini.pdf
- ²² <https://www.pgt.comune.milano.it/vas-rapporto-ambientale/6-valutazione-degli-effetti-ambientali-attesi/63-stima-degli-effetti-ambientali-attesi/631-usi-del-suolo-e-ambiente-costruito/6312-aree-agricole>
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- ²⁷ <https://www.c40.org/cities/milan/>
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